

Interpreting Digital Camera Images for Measuring Night Sky Quality

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Abstract: We are routinely using digital cameras to measure night sky brightness. We have developed a free tool (DiCaLum) to analyse photos. Over the past five years, we have collected high-resolution and high-precision data at locations with minimal light pollution levels. The latest version of DiCaLum contains the conversion parameters we obtained from spectral measurements (Kolláth et al. 2025). The primary representation of the photos is a radiance map on a colour scale. We also represent the data using a 2D colour diagram, which provides information on the airglow at dark locations. In nearly natural conditions, variations in airglow result in significant variations in sky radiance. Therefore, it is essential to use an indicator of the possible airglow, i.e. the actual colour of the sky. During my talk, I will describe the methods and conditions for taking photos for measurements and provide an introduction to the processing of the pictures.

Kolláth, Z., Hajdu, T., Degen, T., Jechow, A. & Sztakovics, J.: "Conversion between measurement units used for night sky quality assessment with multispectral (RGB) cameras", *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 347, 109636 (2025)

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